

FACTORS GOVERNING THE TENSILE STRENGTH OF BASALT FIBRE

Dan XING^{1,2}, Xiong-Yu XI¹, Peng-Cheng MA^{1,2}

¹The Xinjiang Technical Institute of Physics and Chemistry, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Urumqi, 830011, China

²University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, 100049, China

Introduction

➤ **Basalt fibre (BF):** A kind of sodium aluminosilicate filament made from natural basalt rock.

Advantage: Outstanding mechanical properties, high resistance to sound and heat, wide working temperature range, environment-friendly.

Problem: The measured strength is significantly lower than its theoretical value (3000-4840 MPa).

➤ FT-IR and Raman spectroscopy of BF

➤ Effect of sizing on the mechanical properties of BF

Sample	With sizing?	σ (MPa)	σ (N/Tex)	m	Increase (%) ¹
BF-1	No	1220 ± 330	0.51 ± 0.14	3.91	16.4
	Yes	1420 ± 390	0.56 ± 0.15	3.92	
BF-2	No	1440 ± 320	0.56 ± 0.12	5.01	16.7
	Yes	1680 ± 340	0.65 ± 0.13	5.23	
BF-3	No	1630 ± 290	0.64 ± 0.11	5.83	17.2
	Yes	1910 ± 320	0.75 ± 0.13	6.44	
BF-4	No	1690 ± 270	0.64 ± 0.10	6.51	23.1
	Yes	2080 ± 320	0.79 ± 0.12	6.73	
BF-5	No	1730 ± 270	0.66 ± 0.10	6.68	21.4
	Yes	2100 ± 340	0.81 ± 0.13	6.78	
BF-6	No	1750 ± 300	0.68 ± 0.12	7.16	25.7
	Yes	2200 ± 320	0.83 ± 0.12	7.41	
BF-7	No	1890 ± 240	0.73 ± 0.09	7.70	25.9
	Yes	2380 ± 330	0.87 ± 0.12	8.14	

¹ Refers to the increase on the tensile strength after the application of sizing.

➤ Effect of chemical composition on the mechanical properties of BF

Experimental Setups

Results and Discussion

➤ Morphology of BF

BFs with sizing

BFs without sizing

Cross-section of BF

Conclusions

- The tensile strength of BF is mainly dominated by the chemical composition and sizing.
- Al₂O₃ in BF plays a key role in the material composition to benefit the mechanical property of BF.
- A high Fe³⁺/ΣFe can increase the number of defects on the surface of BF with a decreasing of tensile strength.

Acknowledgment